

Examining Possible Future Trajectories of Global Space Sectors

Replication Package - Content

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Category Definitions

Scenario Descriptor	Relevant Categories	Category Definition	Coding Indicators
Actor composition of governance	Start-ups and SME's	Table 1	1.1) Developing Economies (Proportional) 1.2) International Organisations (Proportional) 1.3) Ratio of 'Start-ups and SMEs' to 'large companies'
	Large Companies	Table 2	
	Governments	Table 3	
	Developing Economies	Table 4	
	International Organisations	Table 5	
Governance characteristics	Multilateral and/or Global	Table 6	2.1) Multilateral and/or Global (Proportional) 2.2) Ratio of proportional 'bilateral' to proportional 'minilateral'
	Minilateral	Table 7	
	Bilateral	Table 8	
Industry structure	Economic Sustainability	Table 9	3.0) Economic sustainability
Space-based or ground infrastructures	Space as Common Global Resource	Table 10	4.1) Space as Common Global Resource 4.2) Ownership 4.3) Equity as a priority
	Ownership	Table 11	
	Equity as a priority	Table 12	
Global justice and/or development gap	Diversity and Inclusion	Table 13	5.1) Diversity and Inclusion 5.2) Indigenous Rights 5.3) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
	Indigenous Rights	Table 14	
	Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	Table 15	
Strategies of private actors	Profit-driven Incentives	Table 16	6.0) Ratio of 'profit-driven incentives' to 'value-driven incentives'
	Value-driven Incentives	Table 17	
Impact on Earth's environment	Sustainability on Earth	Table 18	7.0) Sustainability on Earth in combination with ratio of 'using space for Earth's sustainability' to 'impact of space activities on Earth'
	Using Space for Earth's Sustainability	Table 19	
	Impact of Space Activities on Earth	Table 20	
Impact on Space Environment	Sustainability in Space	Table 21	8.0) Sustainability in space
Earth-Space inter-dependency	Sustainability on Earth	Table 18	9.0) Ratio of sustainability on Earth to in space
	Sustainability in Space	Table 21	

Table 1: Category Definition – Start-ups and SME's

Scenario Descriptor	Actor composition of governance
Coding Indicator	Start-ups and SME's
Content description	Mentioning of start-ups and SMEs, both in the context of collaboration and governance
Application of the category	Either if specifically mentioned or if "industry" or "private sector" addressed as a whole
Examples of applications	"[...] while Australia will need to grow capabilities through its start-up and growing space businesses" (Australian Space Agency, 2019, p. 7)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 2: Category Definition – Large Companies

Scenario Descriptor	Actor composition of governance
Coding Indicator	Large Companies
Content description	Mentioning of large and advanced companies
Application of the category	Either if specifically mentioned or if "industry" or "private sector" addressed as a whole
Examples of applications	"Create the conditions for increased diversity and competitiveness of medium and large-scale companies to better balance the size distribution of space companies in the UK" (Government of the United Kingdom, 2024, p. 10)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 3: Category Definition – Governments

Scenario Descriptor	Actor composition of governance
Coding Indicator	Governments
Content description	Collaboration with other countries and governments on an international level
Application of the category	e.g. export and trade agreements or other bi-, mini and/or multilateral agreements
Examples of applications	"Fostering international cooperation within Africa and with the rest of the world as a means of realizing the full value proposition of the space sector." (African Union, 2019, p. 4)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 4: Category Definition – Developing Economies

Scenario Descriptor	Actor composition of governance
Coding Indicator	Developing Economies
Content description	Collaboration with developing economies, also referred to as ‘emerging space-faring nations’
Application of the category	e.g. support of developing economies with workforce development
Examples of applications	“Strengthening international space cooperation that is based on common goals and serves the Belt and Road Initiative, and ensuring that the space industry benefits the Initiative’s participating countries, especially developing countries” (The State Council Information Office of the People’s Republic of China, 2022)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	If coded to this category, then not coded to ‘Governments’

Table 5: Category Definition – International Organisations

Scenario Descriptor	Actor composition of governance
Coding Indicator	International Organisations
Content description	Collaboration with international organisations
Application of the category	e.g. with UN COPUOS
Examples of applications	“NASA was a founding member of the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee and led the committee to establish the first consensus-based international guidelines for mitigating orbital debris.” (NASA, 2024, p. 4)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 6: Category Definition – Multilateral and/or Global

Scenario Descriptor	Governance characteristics
Coding Indicator	Multilateral and/or Global
Content description	Multilateral and or global collaboration
Application of the category	Collaboration based on shared values and potentially through international organisations like the United Nations
Examples of applications	“New Zealand will continue to advocate for effective international rules, norms and standards in space. New Zealand is party to the main international space treaties which are reflected in our domestic laws and policies. [...] New Zealand supports ongoing efforts to advance international agreement on norms, rules and principles of responsible behaviour in space.” (MBIE, 2024a, p. 11)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	If just “International cooperation” mentioned and not inferable from the context whether bi-, mini- and/or multi-lateral, then all of them are coded

Table 7: Category Definition – Minilateral

Scenario Descriptor	Governance characteristics
Coding Indicator	Minilateral
Content description	Minilateral collaboration amongst a sub-set of countries
Application of the category	European Union, African Union and United Kingdom are inherently minilateral. Collaboration with these is thus coded as minilateral.
Examples of applications	“Aotearoa New Zealand is a signatory to the Artemis Accords, an international arrangement led by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) to support peaceful exploration and activity in space” (MBIE, 2023a, p. 21)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	If just “International cooperation” mentioned and not inferable from the context whether bi-, mini- and/or multi-lateral, then all of the are coded. Every collaboration/governance initiative that is not clearly global is coded as minilateral.

Table 8: Category Definition – Bilateral

Scenario Descriptor	Governance characteristics
Coding Indicator	Bilateral
Content description	Bilateral collaboration
Application of the category	Includes partnerships
Examples of applications	“Through UKSA, we are investing in an International Bilateral Fund, which will fund UK space projects with our strategic partners, as well as emerging space nations.” (Government of the United Kingdom, 2023, p. 21)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	If just “International cooperation” mentioned and not inferable from the context whether bi-, mini- and/or multi-lateral, then all of them are coded

Table 9: Category Definition – Economic Sustainability

Scenario Descriptor	Industry structure
Coding Indicator	Economic Sustainability
Content description	Measures and plans to advance economic growth and feasibility
Application of the category	Measures to increase growth, support of the private sector, start-up incubators, workforce development
Examples of applications	“Foster industry according to its ability to sustainably exploit economic potentials.” (Brazilian Space Agency, 2022, p. 11)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 10: Category Definition – Space as Common Global Resource

Scenario Descriptor	Space-based or ground infrastructures
Coding Indicator	Space as Common Global Resource
Content description	Indicators that space is viewed as a common global resource
Application of the category	Assumption that the Artemis Accords do not acknowledge space as a global commons
Examples of applications	“Australia can become a medium to major player in managing the global commons of space” (Australian Academy of Science, 2022, p. 28)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 11: Category Definition – Ownership

Scenario Descriptor	Space-based or ground infrastructures
Coding Indicator	Ownership
Content description	Indicators that governments plan to claim ownership over space resources
Application of the category	e.g. the Artemis Accords
Examples of applications	“Any NGE engaged in such process shall be entitled to possess, own, transport, use, and sell any such asteroid resource or space resource obtained in accordance with applicable law, including the international obligations of India.” (Indian Space Research Organisation, 2023a, p. 7)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 12: Category Definition – Equity as a priority

Scenario Descriptor	Space-based or ground infrastructures
Coding Indicator	Equity as a priority
Content description	Indicators that governments aim for equitable conditions in the context of the space sector
Application of the category	e.g. equitable sharing of resources, equitable access to space today and for future generations (intergenerational equity)
Examples of applications	“further messaging that space is for all humankind” (National Science and Technology Council, 2023, p. 13)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	Does not include workforce equity because this category solely focusses on the view of space. Instead, workforce equity is coded in category ‘Diversity and Inclusion’.

Table 13: Category Definition – Diversity and Inclusion

Main category name	Global justice and/or development gap
Sub-category	Diversity and Inclusion
Content description	Goals and measures aimed at diversity and inclusion
Application of the category	e.g. creating opportunities for a more diverse range of people, addressing barriers for under-represented people
Examples of applications	“[...] fostering an inclusive and supportive environment for African NewSpace founders.” (Space in Africa, 2023b, p. 10)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	This category does not include Indigenous rights as they are distinguished from diversity and inclusion unless a connection is specifically mentioned by the government. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are also not included in this category – Diversity and Inclusion measures have to be specifically mentioned.

Table 14: Category Definition – Indigenous Rights

Scenario Descriptor	Global justice and/or development gap
Coding Indicator	Indigenous Rights
Content description	Goals and measures aimed at Indigenous rights
Application of the category	e.g. partnerships with companies run by Indigenous people, addressing barriers for Indigenous people from education to employment
Examples of applications	<p>“We will foster partnerships with Māori in aerospace through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - our work with Māori businesses and collectives on using aerospace technologies to further regional and national economic development - ensuring Māori can excel in sector opportunities, employment and training - developing sector development initiatives that engage Māori expertise.” (MBIE, 2023a, p. 9)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	Distinct from diversity and inclusion unless a connection is specifically mentioned by the government. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are not included in this category – Indigenous rights have to be specifically mentioned.

Table 15: Category Definition – Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Scenario Descriptor	Global justice and/or development gap
Coding Indicator	Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
Content description	Mentioning of the UN Sustainable Development Goals
Application of the category	e.g. how space activities contribute to SDGs
Examples of applications	“[...] meeting the requirements of the sustainable development goals formulated by the United Nations in coordination with the Ministry of External Affairs” (Indian Space Research Organisation, 2023a, p. 10)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	Only coded if SDGs are specifically mentioned.

Table 16: Category Definition – Profit-driven Incentives

Scenario Descriptor	Strategies of private actors
Coding Indicator	Profit-driven Incentives
Content description	Incentives that are motivated by profit and growth
Application of the category	e.g. business incubation centres
Examples of applications	“In February 2023 we announced c. £5 million in funding to 18 projects which will help the UK space economy to grow and drive levelling up across the UK.” (Government of the United Kingdom, 2023, p. 9)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	Does not include workforce development initiatives because these are covered by category Economic Sustainability. Collaboration with other governments is not included either since this category focusses on actions within one country/government

Table 17: Category Definition – Value-driven Incentives

Scenario Descriptor	Strategies of private actors
Coding Indicator	Value-driven Incentives
Content description	Incentives that are driven by specific values, especially sustainability
Application of the category	e.g. more financial support if space missions sustainable; Space Sustainability Ranking
Examples of applications	“Supporting the intent of His Majesty King Charles III’s initiatives in the Astra Carta, which aims to convene the private sector in creating and accelerating sustainable practices across the global space industry.” (Government of the United Kingdom, 2024, p. 14)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	Excludes general UN conventions or other global agreements since these are coded in categories ‘Multilateral and/or Global’ and ‘International Organisations’

Table 18: Category Definition – Sustainability on Earth

Scenario Descriptor	Impact on Earth’s environment
Coding Indicator	Sustainability on Earth
Content description	Aggregate of the two sub-categories ‘Using Space for Earth's Sustainability’ and ‘Impact of Space Activities on Earth’
Application of the category	Not coded separately but aggregating the two sub-categories
Examples of applications	“fast-growing sector that can make a vital contribution to addressing the continent’s challenges” (African Union, 2019, p. 7)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 19: Category Definition – Using Space for Earth's Sustainability

Scenario Descriptor	Earth-Space interdependency
Coding Indicator	Using Space for Earth's Sustainability
Content description	Ways of using space activities to enhance sustainability on Earth
Application of the category	e.g. Earth observation. Space Weather not coded since this category encompasses activities that are aimed to enhance Earth's sustainability and space weather rather influences systems in space
Examples of applications	"fast-growing sector that can make a vital contribution to addressing the continent's challenges" (African Union, 2019, p. 7)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 20: Category Definition – Impact of Space Activities on Earth

Scenario Descriptor	Earth-Space interdependency
Coding Indicator	Impact of Space Activities on Earth
Content description	Acknowledgement of the impact of space activities on Earth as well as goals and measures to reduce it
Application of the category	e.g. reusable launch vehicles, impact of rocket launches and satellite re-entries, light pollution
Examples of applications	"In the process, sustainability principles will be applied throughout the entire life cycle of the system" (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2023, p. 18)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Table 21: Category Definition – Sustainability in Space

Scenario Descriptor	Impact on Space Environment
Coding Indicator	Sustainability in Space
Content description	Goals and measures to reduce the impact of space activities on the space environment and preserving it for future generations
Application of the category	e.g. orbital debris mitigation, space traffic management, in-orbit satellite servicing
Examples of applications	"UNDERScores that a sustainable and safe space environment is the indispensable condition for continuing humankind's exploration and use of space" (ESA, 2023, p. 4)
Differentiation from other categories (optional)	/

Lists of Key Words per Category

For the process of coding the twenty documents, keywords were defined as indicators for each code. These keywords were informed by the priorly conducted content analysis as well as the background knowledge acquired through the literature review.

This list is not exhaustive and only provided a starting point. Whether a passage actually matched to a category was inferred from the context. All documents were still thoroughly read and coded to cover all passages missed by searching for the keywords.

Table 22: List of Keywords for Actor composition of governance

Start-ups und SME's	Large Companies	Governments	Developing Economies	International Organisations
		cooperat*		
		Agreement OR agreements		
		signatories		
		collaborat*		
business		countr*	developing, developed	UN
commercial		consult*	BRI (Belt and Road Initiative)	United Nations
size		EU, ESA, Europe*	emerging	SDG
enabling		NASA, US		sustainable development organisation, organization
private				
industry				
compan*				
start-up, startup				
small				
medium				
SME*				

Table 23: List of Keywords for Governance characteristics

Bilateral	Minilateral	Multilateral and or Global
	cooperat*	
	agreement, agreements	
	collaborat*	
	international	
	trade export	United Nations UN
partner* bilateral	minilateral Artemis Accords	treat* multilateral
		SDG
		sustainable development

Table 24: List of Keywords for Space-based or ground infrastructures

Space as Common Global Resource	Ownership	Equity as a priority
common	Artemis Accords	equit*
commons	own*	access
resource	in-situ resource*	benefit
domain	ISRU	inclusive
		humanity
		humankind
		future generations

Table 25: List of Keywords for Global justice and/or development gap

Diversity and Inclusion	Indigenous Rights	Sustainable Development Goals
women	Indigenous	SDG
gender	Māori	sustainable development
inclus* (inclusion, inclusive, inclusiveness)	Aboriginal	
divers* (divers, diversity)	Torres Strait Islander people	
	marginalised	
disability, disabilities		

Table 26: List of Keywords for Incentives

Profit-driven Incentives	Value-driven Incentives
invest*	policy OR policies
subsidi*	standard OR standards OR standardisation OR standardization
	incentiv*
barrier OR barriers	practices OR practises
fund*	regulation OR regulatory OR regulate
incubat*	best practice
stimulat*	norm OR norms
foster*	behav*
accel*	
finance OR financing	
scale-up OR upscale	

Table 27: List of Keywords for Sustainability Aspects

Using Space for Earth's Sustainability	Impact of Space Activities on Earth	Sustainability in Space	Economic Sustainability
		sustain*	
		access	
	environment		grow*
	impact		cost
	climate		feasib*
	conserv*		market
	preserv*		revenue
	planet		barrier(s)
	protect		workforce
Observation; EO	reusab*	space traffic management	skill*
challenge		STM	educat*
SDG		frequenc*	sovereign
space weather		space situational awareness; SSA	jobs
monitor		SDG	economic
Earth		debris	invest
			commercial

Analysed Documents

Table 28: List of analysed Documents including Word-Count

Government	Documents	Number of Words	Irrelevant Words
African Union	Space in Africa. (2023). African Space Industry Annual Report, 2023 Edition – Space in Africa. https://spaceinafrica.com/2023/08/28/african-space-industry-annual-report-2023-edition/	984	0
	Space in Africa. (2023). <i>African Space Industry Report 2023—Excerpt</i> .	1885	639
	African Union. (2019). African Space Strategy—For Social, Political and Economic Integration. https://au.int/sites/default/files/documents/37434-doc-au_space_strategy_isbn-electronic.pdf	8710	464
Australia	Australian Academy of Science. (2022). <i>Australia in space: A decadal plan for Australian space science 2021-2030</i> . Australian Academy of Science.	22305	2780
	Australian Space Agency. (2019, April). <i>Australian Civil Space Strategy 2019-2028</i> .	5570	403
Brazil	Brazilian Space Agency. (2022). <i>PNAE Compact Version—National Program For Space Activities 2022-2031</i> .	8383	1352
China	The State Council Information Office of the People’s Republic of China. (2022, January 28). <i>Full Text: China’s Space Program: A 2021 Perspective</i> . https://english.www.gov.cn/archive/whitepaper/202201/28/content_WS61f35b3dc6d09c94e48a467a.html	7683	49
Europe	ESA. (2022). <i>ESA Space Economy 2022 – Creating Value for Europe</i> . https://esamultimedia.esa.int/multimedia/publications/Space_economy_creating_value_for_Europe/esa_space-economy_brochure.pdf	3758	99
	ESA. (2023). <i>Lifting Europe’s Ambitions for a Green and Sustainable Future, Access to Space and Space Exploration</i> . https://esamultimedia.esa.int/docs/resolution_summit2023_EN.pdf	3176	0
France	CNES. (2022). <i>Annual Report 2022</i> .	19437	667
Germany	Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action. (2023). <i>The German Federal Government’s Space Strategy</i> .	21217	304
India	Indian Space Research Organisation. (2023). <i>Indian Space Policy—2023</i> .	2860	561
New Zealand	MBIE. (2023). <i>Aotearoa New Zealand Aerospace Strategy 2023-2030 = Te rautaki Ātea-ā-rangi o Aotearoa 2023-2030</i> .	8024	1901
	MBIE. (2023, November 27). <i>Briefing for the Incoming Minister for Space</i> .	13249	2704
	MBIE. (2024). <i>New Zealand Space and Advanced Aviation Strategy 2024-2030</i> .	2935	425
Russia	Luzin, P. (2024). <i>Russia’s Space Program after 2024</i> .	7131	1591
UK	Government of the United Kingdom. (2023). <i>National Space Strategy in Action</i> .	13623	229

Government	Documents	Number of Words	Irrelevant Words
	Government of the United Kingdom. (2024, March). <i>Space Industrial Plan from ambition to action – advancing UK Space Industry.</i>	7746	157
USA	National Science and Technology Council. (2023, March). <i>National Low Earth Orbit Research and Development Strategy.</i>	5308	915
	NASA. (2024). <i>NASA's Space Sustainability Strategy.</i>	9954	755

Table 29: Total Relevant Words per Government

Governments	Total Relevant Words
African Union	10476
Australia	24692
Brazil	7031
China	7634
Europe	6835
France	18770
Germany	20913
India	2299
NZ	19178
Russia	5540
UK	20983
US	13592

Scale Determination

The scale was based on the minimum and maximum values for each coding indicator resulting from the content analysis as explained in the table below.

Table 30: Detailed Explanations for the Scale Determination

Nr	Indicator	Scale Determination
1.1	Developing Economies (proportional)	Mentioned (> 0%) or Not (= 0%)
1.2	International Organisations (proportional)	5 types of governance actors (start-ups/SMEs, large companies, governments, developing economies and international organisations) → even distribution amongst them would be 1/5 of 100% = 20% → focus on international organisation greater in Earth-Space Sustainability (>20%) than Open Space Scenario (10-20%)
1.3	Ratio of 'Start-ups and SMEs' to 'large companies'	Assumption: If SMEs amount to at least $\frac{3}{4}$ of the total number of large companies, they are likely to exert significant influence.
2.1	Multilateral and or Global (proportional)	3 types of governance characteristics (bilateral, minilateral, multilateral/global) → even distribution amongst them would be 1/3 of 100% = 33% → focus on shared sustainability (global agreements) greater in Earth-Space Sustainability (>33%) than Open Space Scenario (16.5-33%)
2.2	Ratio of proportional 'bilateral' to proportional 'minilateral'	Space Cartel prioritises bilateral agreements, while Gold Rush prioritises minilateral agreements. Open Space involves mixture of both, whereas Earth-Space focusses on multilateral agreements, making this indicator obsolete if indicator 2.1 is greater than 33% (in that case, indicator 2.2 is automatically scored as Earth-Space Sustainability)
3	Economic sustainability	Total indifference of economic growth would be 0% coding, max. value coded is 26.02% → since it is four scenarios, the threshold for indifference was defined as: $\frac{1}{4} * 26.02\% \approx 6.5\%$
4.1	Space as Common Global Resource	Mentioned (> 0%) or Not (= 0%)
4.2	Ownership	– Space Cartel & Gold Rush: ownership mentioned (> 0%) and space not seen as global commons (indicator 4.1 = 0%) – Open Space: ownership mentioned (> 0%) but space seen as global commons (indicator 4.1 > 0%) since this potentially leads to unequal distribution and ineffective coordination between in-space and on Earth – Earth-Space: ownership not mentioned (= 0%)
4.3	Equity as a priority	– Space Cartel & Gold Rush: equity not mentioned (= 0%) and space not seen as global commons (indicator 4.1 = 0%) – Open Space: equity not mentioned (= 0%) but space seen as global commons (indicator 4.1 > 0%) since this potentially leads to unequal distribution and ineffective coordination between in-space and on Earth – Earth-Space: equity mentioned (> 0%)
5.1	Diversity and Inclusion	Development Gap gradually decreases in the scenarios from Space Cartel to Gold Rush to Open Space to Earth-Space → thresholds were defined as increments of one-quarter of the coding-range, with the minimum value set to 0% to represent the widest development gap $\frac{1}{4} * 3.34\% \approx 0.84\%$

Nr	Indicator	Scale Determination
5.2	Indigenous Rights	<p>Similar approach as for indicator 5.1 → thresholds were defined as increments of one-quarter of the coding-range, with the minimum value set to 0% to represent the widest development gap</p> $\frac{1}{4} * 2.27\% \approx 0.57\%$
5.3	Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	<p>Similar approach as for indicators 5.1 and 5.2 → thresholds were defined as increments of one-quarter of the coding-range, with the minimum value set to 0% to represent the widest development gap</p> $\frac{1}{4} * 1.76\% \approx 0.44\%$
6	Ratio of 'profit-driven incentives' to 'value-driven incentives'	<p>Priority of profit gradually decreases in the scenarios from Space Cartel (high priority) and Gold Rush (high) to Open Space (medium) to Earth-Space (low) → thresholds were defined as increments of one-third of the coding-range, with the minimum value set to 0% to represent absence of profit-driven incentives</p> $\frac{1}{3} * 4.5 = 1.5$
7	Sustainability on Earth	<p>With a coding range of roughly 30% and the scenarios differentiating between the two states of severe and minimal degradation of Earth's environment, a threshold of 10% coding ratio was assumed to be sufficient to avoid Earth's degradation</p>
	Ratio of 'using space for Earth's sustainability' to 'impact of space activities'	<p>This indicator was applied in combination with category 'Sustainability on Earth' to distinguish between the Gold Rush and Earth-Space Sustainability scenario. While the former prioritises Earth's development, the latter prioritises both Earth's development and the impact of space activities. The threshold was defined as $\frac{1}{2}$ of the range:</p> $\frac{1}{2} * 32.6 = 16.3$
8	Sustainability in space	<p>Similar to category 'Sustainability on Earth', the scenarios distinguish two states of the impact on the space environment (severe and minimal degradation). Thus, the same threshold of 10% was applied to this indicator despite the coding range being higher than for category 'Sustainability on Earth' (roughly 40%)</p>
9	Ratio of 'sustainability on Earth' to 'sustainability in space'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Space Cartel: low interdependence (prioritises neither sustainability on Earth nor in space) → ratio ≈ 1 and coding for both categories below threshold of 10% – Gold Rush: low interdependence (does not prioritise sustainability in space) → ratio $\gg 1$ – Open Space: low interdependence (does not prioritise sustainability on Earth) (ratio $\ll 1$) – Earth-Space: high interdependence (prioritises sustainability on Earth and in space equally) → ratio ≈ 1 and coding for both categories above threshold of 10%

Mapping Examples

Table 31: Mapping the African Union

Nr	Descriptor	Indicator	Value	Space Cartel	Earth-Centric Gold Rush	Open Space/ Space Utopia	Earth-Space Sustainability	X-Score (Mean)	Y-Score (Mean)	Weighting	Weighted X-Score	Weighted Y-Score
				X = -1 Y = -1	X = -1 Y = +1	X = +1 Y = -1	X = +1 Y = +1					
1.1	Actor composition of governance	Developing Economies (proportional)	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
1.2		International Organisations (proportional)	23.81%				X	1.00	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.33
1.3		Ratio of 'Start-ups and SMEs' to 'large companies'	1.11			X	X	1.00	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.00
2.1	Governance characteristics	Multilateral and or Global (proportional)	34.79%				X	1.00	1.00	0.5	0.50	0.50
2.2		Ratio of proportional 'bilateral' to proportional 'minilateral'	1.74				X	1.00	1.00	0.5	0.50	0.50
3	Industry structure	Economic sustainability	9.95%	X	X	X		-0.33	-0.33	1	-0.33	-0.33
4.1	Space-based or ground infrastructures	Space as Common Global Resource	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
4.2		Ownership	0.00%				X	1.00	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.33
4.3		Equity as a priority	0.67%				X	1.00	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.33
5.1	Global justice and/or development gap	Diversity and Inclusion	1.26%		X			-1.00	1.00	0.33	-0.33	0.33
5.2		Indigenous Rights	0.37%	X				-1.00	-1.00	0.33	-0.33	-0.33
5.3		Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	0.74%			X		-1.00	1.00	0.33	-0.33	0.33
6	Strategies of private actors	Ratio of 'profit-driven incentives' to 'value-driven incentives'	2.09			X		1.00	-1.00	1	1.00	-1.00
7	Impact on Earth's environment	Sustainability on Earth	27.84%		X			-1.00	1.00	1	-1.00	1.00
		Ratio of 'using space for Earth's sustainability' to 'impact of space activities on Earth'	25.18									
8	Impact on Space Environment	Sustainability in space	3.73%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	1	-1.00	0.00
9	Earth-Space interdependency	Ratio of sustainability on Earth to in space	7.46		X			-1.00	1.00	1	-1.00	1.00
Total											-1.67	3.00

Table 32: Mapping Brazil

Nr	Descriptor	Indicator	Value	Space Cartel	Earth-Centric Gold Rush	Open Space/ Space Utopia	Earth-Space Sustainability	X-Score (Mean)	Y-Score (Mean)	Weighting	Weighted X-Score	Weighted Y-Score
				X = -1 Y = -1	X = -1 Y = +1	X = +1 Y = -1	X = +1 Y = +1					
1.1	Actor composition of governance	Developing Economies (proportional)	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
1.2		International Organisations (proportional)	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
1.3		Ratio of 'Start-ups and SMEs' to 'large companies'	1.18			X	X	1.00	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.00
2.1	Governance characteristics	Multilateral and or Global (proportional)	9.15%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.5	-0.50	0.00
2.2		Ratio of proportional 'bilateral' to proportional 'minilateral'	2.37	X				-1.00	-1.00	0.5	-0.50	-0.50
3	Industry structure	Economic sustainability	15.18%	X	X	X		-0.33	-0.33	1	-0.33	-0.33
4.1	Space-based or ground infrastructures	Space as Common Global Resource	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
4.2		Ownership	0.00%				X	1.00	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.33
4.3		Equity as a priority	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
5.1	Global justice and/or development gap	Diversity and Inclusion	0.38%	X				-1.00	-1.00	0.33	-0.33	-0.33
5.2		Indigenous Rights	0.00%	X				-1.00	-1.00	0.33	-0.33	-0.33
5.3		Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	0.00%	X				-1.00	-1.00	0.33	-0.33	-0.33
6	Strategies of private actors	Ratio of 'profit-driven incentives' to 'value-driven incentives'	3.86	X	X			-1.00	0.00	1	-1.00	0.00
7	Impact on Earth's environment	Sustainability on Earth	3.75%	X		X		0.00	-1.00	1	0.00	-1.00
		Ratio of 'using space for Earth's sustainability' to 'impact of space activities on Earth'	3.15									
8	Impact on Space Environment	Sustainability in space	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	1	-1.00	0.00
9	Earth-Space interdependency	Ratio of sustainability on Earth to in space	3.75		X			-1.00	1.00	1	-1.00	1.00
Total											-6.00	-1.50

Table 33: Mapping the USA

Nr	Descriptor	Indicator	Value	Space Cartel X = -1 Y = -1	Earth-Centric Gold Rush X = -1 Y = +1	Open Space/ Space Utopia X = +1 Y = -1	Earth-Space Sustainability X = +1 Y = +1	X-Score (Mean)	Y-Score (Mean)	Weighting	Weighted X-Score	Weighted Y-Score
1.1	Actor composition of governance	Developing Economies (proportional)	0.86%			X	X	1.00	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.00
1.2		International Organisations (proportional)	6.01%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
1.3		Ratio of 'Start-ups and SMEs' to 'large companies'	1.11			X	X	1.00	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.00
2.1	Governance characteristics	Multilateral and or Global (proportional)	21.49%			X		1.00	-1.00	0.5	0.50	-0.50
2.2		Ratio of proportional 'bilateral' to proportional 'minilateral'	0.91			X		1.00	-1.00	0.5	0.50	-0.50
3	Industry structure	Economic sustainability	9.74%	X	X	X		-0.33	-0.33	1	-0.33	-0.33
4.1	Space-based or ground infrastructures	Space as Common Global Resource	0.00%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
4.2		Ownership	0.04%	X	X			-1.00	0.00	0.33	-0.33	0.00
4.3		Equity as a priority	2.46%				X	1.00	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.33
5.1	Global justice and/or development gap	Diversity and Inclusion	1.49%		X			-1.00	1.00	0.33	-0.33	0.33
5.2		Indigenous Rights	0.00%	X				-1.00	-1.00	0.33	-0.33	-0.33
5.3		Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	0.00%	X				-1.00	-1.00	0.33	-0.33	-0.33
6	Strategies of private actors	Ratio of 'profit-driven incentives' to 'value-driven incentives'	0.19				X	1.00	1.00	1	1.00	1.00
7	Impact on Earth's environment	Sustainability on Earth	2.94%	X		X		0.00	-1.00	1	0.00	-1.00
		Ratio of 'using space for Earth's sustainability' to 'impact of space activities on Earth'	0.24									
8	Impact on Space Environment	Sustainability in space	41.57%			X	X	1.00	0.00	1	1.00	0.00
9	Earth-Space interdependency	Ratio of sustainability on Earth to in space	0.07			X		1.00	-1.00	1	1.00	-1.00
Total											2.67	-2.33